

USING MODERN PEDAGOGICAL METHODS IN DEVELOPING CONFLICT COMPETENCE IN FUTURE EDUCATORS

Kamoldinov Muhammadsodiq Bakhtiyorovich

International Institute of Food Technology and Engineering, Fergana, Uzbekistan
Orcid ID: 0009-0000-2945-6595

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17197170>

Abstract: The article studies the theoretical and methodological foundations of the development of conflictological competence in future teachers, the practical methodological system of developing conflictological competence in future teachers, the effectiveness of developing conflictological competence in future teachers. The practical methodological system of developing conflictological competence in future teachers is also analyzed.

Key words: conflictological competence, competence, pedagogical, theoretical and methodological basis, improvement, technological, model, methodological system, motivational and axiological, cognitive, interactive technologies.

Introduction

Despite the existence of diverse approaches to defining the components of conflictological competence in future teachers within the framework of the discipline “*Pedagogical Conflictology*”, certain commonalities can be observed across them. In particular, the components of conflictological competence may be analyzed in terms of cognitive, emotional, communicative, and behavioral aspects; components of conflictological preparedness; as well as communicative abilities, positive attitudes, empathy, skills of constructive conflict resolution, and the ability to analyze situations. Based on the discipline “*Pedagogical Conflictology*”, the model for developing conflictological competence in future teachers encompasses conceptual, organizational-technological, and analytical-corrective blocks. These blocks reflect the goals, content, criteria, and stages that serve as the theoretical and technological foundations for fostering conflictological competence.

Literature Review and Methods

The theoretical and methodological foundations for developing conflictological competence in future teachers, the practical methodological system of its formation, and issues related to enhancing its effectiveness have been studied by scholars such as J. Burton, F. Dukes, L. Coser, G. Mead, T. Gordon, K. Thomas, A. Eagly, A. Antsupov, A. Belkin, V. Zhuravlev, E. Kirshbaum, A. Lobanov, I. Marinovskaya, V. Tsvetkov, Sh. Abdullaeva, D. Ro'zieva, N.

Azizkhodjaeva, M. Akhmedova, M. Davletshin, S. Jalilova, Kh. Ibragimov, Kh. Karimov, V. Karimova, D. Narziqulova, Z. Salieva, and G. Tuychieva.

Results and Discussion

The use of the “problem” method in the process of corrective-educational activities helps students acquire the skill of identifying the underlying causes of any issue before attempting to resolve it, and only then selecting the necessary strategies and methods.

The purpose of the “*Labyrinth*” method is to help students develop the ability to navigate various situations encountered in their social activities while preserving their reputation, to assess situations accurately, to find appropriate solutions quickly, to enhance relevant skills, to strengthen their critical thinking and speech activities, and to cultivate a culture of communication.

Procedure of the Activity:

Before the session begins, the group mentor arranges chairs in a circle for the students. Placing a basket or a pot with flowers in the center of the circle is considered advisable, as such an arrangement helps make the activity engaging and lively.

After the students take their seats in the circle, the session begins with a brief conversation led by the mentor about the diversity of human activity and the variety of events, phenomena, and situations it encompasses. As an example, the mentor discusses how certain qualities manifest in student activities, their significance in the moral and ethical development of the individual, and situations where such qualities may be insufficiently developed. Students are then asked to suggest possible solutions (at least three), choose one of them, and explain their choice.

Subsequently, students are invited to recall from their personal experience a problematic situation they encountered in educational or upbringing contexts, and to propose at least three possible solutions. With the assistance of the mentor, each student presents their prepared situation or problem orally to the group. The mentor allocates a specific amount of time (up to 5–10 minutes) for finding solutions. During this time, group members work on identifying possible resolutions. Once the time has expired, the students present their answers. For instance, a situation selected by one student is repeated, and the rest of the group members take turns offering their solutions and opinions on the most appropriate resolution. The mentor also shares their perspective on the situation, synthesizing the various viewpoints expressed.

At the conclusion of the session, the mentor evaluates each student's contribution and the group's collective work, provides recommendations on aspects to prioritize when resolving problems, and formally closes the activity.

Description of the "Dialogue" Method

This method is designed to encourage students to think independently, to express their ideas freely, and to cultivate a culture of constructive debate.

Objective of the Method:

Based on a selected topic or issue, the method aims to identify students' opinions and attitudes, to assist them in independently reaching a shared conclusion, to help them make sound judgments, to provide conditions for free debate, and to teach them how to engage in and sustain meaningful dialogue.

Application of the Method.

In the process of educational and corrective work, it is considered appropriate to divide students into small groups when applying this method, with the sessions being conducted either in the classroom or in a natural environment.

Materials used in the session: flip chart paper, markers, and felt-tip pens.

Procedure of the session: Prior to the commencement of the activity, the group supervisor introduces students to the requirements and rules of interaction and debate. Subsequently, the supervisor explains the content of each stage of the session and the tasks to be carried out. The supervisor then divides the students into small groups according to the thematic directions of the session; each subgroup begins preparing within its own direction. To interact with other groups, the subgroups prepare various visual aids, collect relevant narratives, and compile the opinions of scholars and thinkers. Dialogue between the subgroups then begins on the main topic and its directions. Throughout this process, the supervisor purposefully guides the discussion. After the subgroups present their perspectives on the main theme, the supervisor provides his or her own reflections, thereby concluding the discussion. At the end of the session, the supervisor analyzes the performance of each group, expresses appreciation for their participation, and formally closes the activity.

On the prevention of pedagogical conflicts.

Conflict prevention in pedagogical practice requires an analytical and alternative approach to situational analysis. In addressing this task, it is advisable to use the case study strategy. The term *case study* originates from the English words *case*—a concrete situation, and *study*—learning. It refers to a

teaching method based on the study and analysis of specific situations and the attainment of socially meaningful outcomes. Unlike the problem-based learning method, this strategy emphasizes making concrete decisions based on the examination of real situations.

Conclusion.

Overall, for the teaching and educational process organized on the basis of the case study method in continuous education to be effective, two essential conditions are required: (1) the preparation of a case task that takes into account the age as well as pedagogical and psychological characteristics of learners, and (2) the development of a clear methodology for its application in the educational process. The use of this method enhances students' interest in the subject being studied and cultivates their research, decision-making, communicative, and creative skills.

In summary, the effective use of the technology of organizing educational and corrective activities contributes to the successful resolution of conflicts arising in the pedagogical process and accelerates the preparation of students for their future professional practice.

References:

1. Coser, L. Conflict: Social Aspects. In D. Sills (Ed.), International Encyclopedia of the Social Sciences (Vol. 3, pp. 232–236). USA, 1998.
2. Eagly, A. H., & Johnson, B. T. (2017). Gender and leadership style: A meta-analysis. *Psychological Bulletin*, 108(2), 233–256.
3. Thomas, K. W., & Kilmann, R. H. (1999). Thomas-Kilmann Conflict Mode Instrument. XI COM, 39 p.
4. Kuzina, A. A. (2007). Education of Conflictological Competence of High School Students (Abstract of Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences Dissertation). Moscow.
5. Kuzina, A. A. (2007). Education of Conflictological Competence of High School Students (Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences Dissertation). Moscow, 176 p.
6. Sgonnikova, E. M. (2010). Development of Conflictological Competence of Future Teachers (Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences Dissertation). Shadrinsk.